

Smarandache Soft-Neutrosophic-Near Ring and Soft-Neutrosophic Bi-Ideal

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Abstract. In this paper, we introduced Smarandache-2-algebraic structure of Soft Neutrosophic Near-ring namely Smarandache-Soft Neutrosophic Near-ring. A Smarandache-2-algebraic structure on a set N means a weak algebraic structure S_1 on N such that there exist a proper subset M of N , Which is embedded with a stronger algebraic structure S_2 , stronger algebraic structure means satisfying more axioms, that is $S_1 \ll S_2$, by proper subset one can understand a subset different from the empty set, from the unit element if any, from the Whole set. We define Smarandache-Soft Neutrosophic Near-ring and obtain the some of its characterization through bi-ideals.

Keywords: Soft neutrosophic near-ring, soft neutrosophic near-field, smarandache -soft neutrosophic near- ring, soft neutrosophic bi-ideals

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1. Introduction

In order that, New notions are introduced in algebra to better study the congruence in number theory by Florentinsmarandache [2]. By <proper subset> of a set A we consider a set P included in A , and different from A , different from empty set, and from the unit element in A -if any they rank the algebraic structures using an order relationship:

They say that the algebraic structures $S_1 \ll S_2$ if: both are defined on the same set; all S_1 laws are also S_2 laws; all axioms of an S_1 law are accomplished by the corresponding S_2 law; S_2 law accomplish strictly more axioms than S_1 laws, or S_2 has more laws than S_1 .

For example: Semi group \ll Monoid \ll group \ll ring \ll field, or Semi group \ll to commutative semi group, ring \ll unitary ring etc. They define a general special structure to be a structure SM on a set A , different from a structure SN , such that a proper subset of A is a structure, where $SM \ll SN$. In addition we have published [6,7,8].

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. Let $\langle NUI \rangle$ be a neutrosophic near-ring and (F, A) be a soft set over $\langle NUI \rangle$. Then (F, A) is called soft neutrosophic near-ring if and only if $F(a)$ is a neutrosophic sub near-ring of $\langle NUI \rangle$ for all $a \in A$.

Definition 2.2. Let $K(I) = \langle KUI \rangle$ be a neutrosophic near-field and let (F, A) be a soft set over $K(I)$. Then (F, A) is said to be soft neutrosophic near-field if and only if $F(a)$ is a neutrosophic sub near-field of $K(I)$ for all $a \in A$.

Definition 2.3. Let (F, A) be a soft neutrosophic zero symmetric near-ring over $\langle N \cup I \rangle$, which contains a distributive element $F(a_1) \neq 0$. Then (F, A) is a near-field if and only if for each $F(a) \neq 0$ in (F, A) , $(F, A)F(a) = (F, A)$.

Now we have introduced our basic concept, called smarandache–soft neutrosophic–near ring.

Definition 2.4. A Soft neutrosophic –near ring is said to be Smarandache –soft neutrosophic –near ring, if a proper subset of it is a soft neutrosophic –near field with respect to the same induced operations.

Definition 2.5. Let (F, A) be a Smarandache - soft Neutrosophic near –ring over $\langle NUI \rangle$. The two subsets (H, A) and (G, A) of (F, A) the product is defined as $(H, A)(G, A) = \{ H(a_1) G(a) / H(a_1) \text{ in } (H, A), G(a) \text{ in } (G, A) \}$. Also we define another operation “*” on the class of subsets of (F, A) given by $(H, A) * (G, A) = \{ H(a_1) (H(a_2) + G(a)) - H(a_1) H(a_2) / H(a_1), H(a_2) \text{ in } (H, A), G(a) \text{ in } (G, A) \}$, where (H, A) is a proper subset of (F, A) , which is a Soft Neutrosophic near-field.

Definition 2.6. Let (F, A) be a Smarandache - soft Neutrosophic near –ring over $\langle NUI \rangle$, then a subgroup (L_B, A) of $((F, A), +)$ is said to be a Soft Neutrosophic Bi –ideal of (F, A) if $(L_B, A)(F, A)(L_B, A) \cap ((L_B, A)(F, A)) * (L_B, A) \subseteq (L_B, A)$.

3. Preliminary results on soft Neutrosophic bi-ideals

Here we obtain certain results for our future use.

Proposition 3.1. If (L_B, A) be a Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideal of a Smarandache-soft Neutrosophic-near ring (F, A) over $\langle NUI \rangle$ and (F_1, A) is a Smarandache-soft Neutrosophic sub near ring of (F, A) , then $(L_B, A) \cap (F_1, A)$ is a Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideal of (F_1, A) .

Proof: Since (F, A) be a Smarandache -soft Neutrosophic near –ring over $\langle NUI \rangle$, then by definition, there exists a proper subset (H, A) , which is Soft neutrosophic near field.

Since (L_B, A) is a Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideal of (F, A) ,

$$(L_B, A)(F, A)(L_B, A) \cap ((L_B, A)(F, A)) * (L_B, A) \subseteq (L_B, A),$$

$$\text{let } (L_{B_1}, A) = (L_B, A) \cap (F_1, A),$$

$$\text{now } (L_{B_1}, A)(F_1, A)(L_{B_1}, A) \cap ((L_{B_1}, A)(F_1, A)) * (L_{B_1}, A) = ((L_B, A) \cap (F_1, A)) (F_1, A)$$

$$((L_B, A) \cap (F_1, A)) \cap ((L_B, A) \cap (F_1, A))(F_1, A) * ((L_B, A) \cap (F_1, A))$$

$$\subseteq (L_B, A)(F_1, A)(L_B, A) \cap (F_1, A) \cap ((L_B, A)(F_1, A)) * (L_B, A)$$

$$\subseteq (L_B, A) \cap (F_1, A) = (L_{B_1}, A). \text{ Hence } (L_{B_1}, A) \text{ is a Soft neutrosophic bi-ideal of } (F_1, A).$$

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Proposition 3.2. Let (F,A) be a Smarandache- soft Neutrosophic near –ring over $\langle NUI \rangle$, which is zerosymmetric. A subgroup (L_B,A) of (F,A) is a Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideal if and only if $(L_B,A)(F,A)(L_B,A) \subseteq (L_B,A)$.

Proof: Since (F,A) be a Smarandache - soft Neutrosophic near –ring over $\langle NUI \rangle$, then by definition, there exists a proper subset (H,A) , which is Soft neutrosophic near field.

For a subgroup (L_B,A) of $((F,A),+)$, if $(L_B,A)(F,A)(L_B,A) \subseteq (L_B,A)$, then (L_B,A) is a Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideal of (F,A) .

Conversly, if (L_B,A) is a Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideal, we have

$$(L_B,A)(F,A)(L_B,A) \cap ((L_B,A)(F,A)) * (L_B,A) \subseteq (L_B,A),$$

since (F,A) is Soft Neutrosophic zero symmetric near ring, $(F,A) (L_B,A) \subseteq (F,A) * (L_B,A)$, we get

$$(L_B,A)(F,A)(L_B,A) = (L_B,A)(F,A)(L_B,A) \cap (L_B,A)(F,A)(L_B,A)$$

$$\subseteq (L_B,A)(F,A)(L_B,A) \cap ((L_B,A) (F,A)) * (L_B,A) \subseteq (L_B,A).$$

Proposition 3.3. Let (F,A) be a Smarandache-soft Neutrosophic near–ring over $\langle NUI \rangle$, which is zero symmetric. If (L_B,A) is a Soft neutrosophic bi-ideal of (F,A) , then $(L_B,A)H(n_1)$ and $H(n_2)(L_B,A)$ are Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideals of (F,A) , where $H(n_1), H(n_2)$ in (H,A) and $H(n_2)$ is distributive element in (H,A) , where (H,A) is a proper subset of (F,A) , which is a Soft Neutrosophic near-field.

Proof: Clearly $(L_B,A)H(n_1)$ is a subgroup of $((F,A),+)$ and

$$(L_B,A)H(n_1) (H,A) (L_B,A)H(n_1) \subseteq (L_B,A) (H,A) (L_B,A)H(n_1) \subseteq (L_B,A)H(n_1),$$

we get $(L_B,A) H(n_1)$ is a Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideal of (F,A) .

Again $H(n_2) (L_B,A)$ is a subgroup since $H(n_2)$ is distributive in (H,A) and

$$H(n_2) (L_B,A) (H,A) H(n_2) (L_B,A) \subseteq H(n_2) (L_B,A)(H,A)(L_B,A) \subseteq H(n_1) (L_B,A).$$

Thus $H(n_2)(L_B,A)$ is a Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideal of (F,A) .

Corollary 3.1. If (L_B,A) is a Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideal of a Smarandache-soft neutrosophic-near ring (F,A) over $\langle NUI \rangle$ and $L_B(a)$ is a distributive element in (F,A) , then $L_B(a) (L_B,A) H(a)$ is a Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideal of (F,A) , where $H(a)$ in (H,A) , where (H,A) is a proper subset of (F,A) , which is a Soft Neutrosophic near-field.

4. Minimal soft neutrosophic bi-ideals and soft neutrosophic near field

Definition 4.1. A Smarandache - soft Neutrosophic near –ring (F,A) over $\langle NUI \rangle$ is said to be L_B -simple if it has no proper Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideals.

In this section we obtain a characterization of Smarandache- soft neutrosophic near-ring using Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideals.

Lemma 4.1. Let (F,A) be a Smarandache- soft Neutrosophic near –ring over $\langle NUI \rangle$ with more than one element .Then the following conditions are equivalent:

- (i) (H,A) is a Soft Neutrosophic near-field,
- (ii) (H,A) is L_B - simple, $H(d) \neq \{0\}$ and for $0 \neq H(n_1)$ in (H,A) there exists an element $H(n_2)$ of (H,A) such that $H(n_2)H(n_1) \neq 0$.

where (H,A) is a proper subset of (F,A) , which is a Soft Neutrosophic near-field.

Proof: (i) \Rightarrow (ii) If (H,A) is a Soft Neutrosophic near -field, then $\{0\}$ and (H,A) are the only Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideals of (H,A) . For if $0 \neq (L_B,A)$ is a Soft neutrosophic bi-

ideal of (H,A) , then, for $0 \neq L_B(a)$ in (L_B,A) we get $(H,A) = (H,A)L_B(a)$ and $(H,A) = L_B(a)(H,A)$. Now $(H,A) = (H,A)^2 = (L_B(a)(H,A))(H,A)L_B(a) \subseteq L_B(a)(H,A)L_B(a) \subseteq (L_B,A)$, since (L_B,A) is a Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideal of (H,A) . i.e. $(H,A) = (L_B,A)$. Hence (H,A) is L_B -simple and the identity element in (H,A) satisfies the required condition.

(ii) \Rightarrow (i)

Since $H(d) \neq \{0\}$ we get (H,A) is not constant. We know that $H(0)$ is a Soft neutrosophic bi-ideal of (H,A) and since (H,A) is L_B -simple we get $(H,A) = H(0)$. Let $0 \neq H(n_1)$ in (H,A) , by proposition 3, $(H,A)H(n_1)$ is a Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideal of (H,A) and $0 \neq H(n_2) \in H(n_1)$ in $(H,A)H(n_1)$ for some $H(n_2)$ in (H,A) . Hence $(H,A)H(n_1) = (H,A)$. Therefore we have (H,A) is a Soft Neutrosophic near field.

Theorem 4.1. If a minimal (F,A) -subgroup (H_{min},A) of a Smarandache-Soft Neutrosophic zero symmetric near ring (F,A) over $\langle NUI \rangle$ which is zerosymmetric has a non-zero distributive idempotent element $H(e)$, then $H(e)(H_{min},A)$ is a Multiplicative subgroup of (F,A) . Moreover it is a minimal Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideal of (F,A) .

Proof: Since (F,A) be a Smarandache-soft Neutrosophic near-ring over $\langle NUI \rangle$, then by definition, there exists a proper subset (H,A) , which is Soft neutrosophic near field.

By Proposition 3, $H(e)(H_{min},A)$ is a Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideal of (F,A) .

Clearly $H(e)$ is a left identity for $H(e)(H_{min},A)$. If $H(e)H_{min}(a) \neq 0$, for some $H_{min}(a)$ in (H_{min},A) , then the non-zero $(H_{min},A)(H(e)H_{min}(a))$ is a (F,A) -subgroup of (F,A) and also $(H_{min},A)(H(e)H_{min}(a)) \subseteq (H_{min},A)$. Thus we get $(H_{min},A)(H(e)H_{min}(a)) = (H_{min},A)$, which implies that $(H(e)(H_{min},A))(H(e)H_{min}(a)) = H(e)(H_{min},A)$, i.e. the non-zero element $H(e)H_{min}(a)$ has a left inverse $H(e)H(t)$ such that $(H(e)H(t))(H(e)H_{min}(a)) = H(e)$. Hence the non-zero elements of $H(e)(H_{min},A)$ form a multiplicative subgroup of (H,A) . We have that $H(e)(H_{min},A)$ is a Soft Neutrosophic near field.

Now $H(e)(H_{min},A) \subseteq H(0)$. If (L_{B_1},A) is a Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideal of (F,A) such that $\{0\} \neq (L_{B_1},A) \subseteq H(e)(H_{min},A)$, then $(L_{B_1},A)(H(e)(H_{min},A))(L_{B_1},A) \subseteq (L_{B_1},A)(F,A)(L_{B_1},A) \subset (L_{B_1},A)$, which implies that (L_{B_1},A) is Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideal of $H(e)(H_{min},A)$.

But $H(e)(H_{min},A)$ is a Soft neutrosophic near field and so by lemma 1, we get $H(e)(H_{min},A)$ is L_B -simple. Hence, $H(e)(H_{min},A) = (L_{B_1},A)$. i.e. $H(e)(H_{min},A)$ is a minimal Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideal of (F,A) .

Lemma 4.2. If a Minimal Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideal (L_B,A) of Smarandache-soft neutrosophic near ring (F,A) over $\langle NUI \rangle$ which is zero symmetric contains a distributive element $L_B(a)$ such that $L_B(a)$ is neither a left zero divisor nor right zero divisor, then (F,A) must have a two-sided identity.

Proof: Since (F,A) be a Smarandache-soft Neutrosophic near-ring over $\langle NUI \rangle$.

Then by definition (H,A) is a proper subset of (F,A) , which is a Soft Neutrosophic near-field.

Clearly $(L_B(a))^3 \neq 0$ and $(L_B(a))^3$ in $L_B(a)(F,A)L_B(a) \subseteq (L_B,A)$. By corollary 4, $L_B(a)(F,A)L_B(a)$ is a Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideal of (F,A) and $L_B(a)(F,A)L_B(a) = (L_B,A)$, since (L_B,A) is minimal. Therefore $L_B(a) = L_B(a)F(a)L_B(a)$ for some $F(a)$ in (F,A) .

For $F(x), F(y)$ in (F,A) , we have $F(x) = F(x)L_B(a)F(a)$ and $F(y) = F(a)L_B(a)F(y)$,

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Since $L_B(a)$ is neither a left zero divisor nor a right zero divisor.
 i.e. $F(a)L_B(a)$ and $L_B(a)F(a)$ are left and right identities for (F,A) respectively and
 hence $F(a)L_B(a) = L_B(a)F(a)$ is the required identity element in (F,A)

Now we prove the main theorem of this paper.

Theorem 4.2. Let (F,A) be a Smarandache-soft neutrosophic near ring over $\langle NUI \rangle$, which is zerosymmetric. Then (H,A) is a Soft Neutrosophicnear field if and only if (H,A) has a distributive element which is neither a left zero divisor nor a right zero divisor and which is contained in a minimal Soft Neutrosophicbi-ideal (L_B,A) of (F,A) .

Proof: Since (F,A) be a Smarandache -soft Neutrosophic near -ring over $\langle NUI \rangle$.
 Then by definition (H,A) is a proper subset of (F,A) , which is a Soft Neutrosophic near-field. If (H,A) is a Soft Neutrosophic near field ,then (H,A) itself is a minimal Soft Neutrosophic bi-ideal satisfying the required conditions.

Conversely, let (L_B,A) be a minimal Soft Neutrosophicbi-ideal of (F,A) containing a distributive element $H(d)$ which is neither a left nor a right zero divisor .

By lemma 3, (H,A) contains a identity $H(e)$.

Again by corollary 4, $H(d)^2 (H,A) H(d)^2$ is a Soft Neutrosophicbi-ideal and $0 \neq H(d)^2 (H,A) H(d)^2 \subseteq (L_B,A)(H,A)(L_B,A) \subseteq (L_B,A)$.

Since (L_B,A) is a minimal we get $(L_B,A) = H(d)^2 (H,A) H(d)^2$.

Now $H(d)$ in $(L_B,A) = H(d)^2 (H,A) H(d)^2$ implies that $H(d) = H(n)H(d)^2$ for some $H(n)$ in (H,A) .

But $H(d) = H(e)H(d)$ and so $H(e) = H(n)H(d)$

i.e. $H(e)$ in $(H,A)H(d)$. Similarly we get $H(e)$ in $H(d)(H,A)$.

Therefore $H(e) = H(e)^2$ in $(H(d)(H,A)) ((H,A)H(d)) \subseteq H(d) (H,A) H(d) \subseteq (L_B,A)$, whence $(H,A) = H(e)(H,A)H(e) \subseteq (L_B,A) (H,A)(L_B,A) \subseteq (L_B,A)$, that is $(H,A) = (L_B,A)$.

This relation and minimality of (L_B,A) implies that (H,A) is L_B - simple and so (H,A) is a Soft Neutrosophic near -field by lemma 1.

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